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One of the urgent tasks when applying the principles of metrological support in Industry 4.0 is the need to develop a concept for cost-effective calibration of MEMS sensors to assign reliable values of measurement uncertainties at the output of sensors. The “big is bad” principle aims to use many measuring instruments to compensate for the unsatisfactory metrological characteristics of individual sensors. Typically, this is based on the assumption that, through skillful use of intelligent processing techniques, measurement templates can be used in the same way as measurement results from individual reference sensors. However, real verification of this assumption, as well as comparison of measurement results on other measurement channels, is possible only taking into account measurement uncertainty and traceability to SI units [1-12].

Existing calibration methods are usually too complex and expensive for MEMS sensors. Therefore, one approach is to implement batch calibration methods, where multiple sensors are calibrated simultaneously to save time and money. This concept is already used in periodic metrological verification of MEMS sensors and in their automated testing. For this purpose, calibrated reference sensors are used, installed at the measurement object. Then the sensors subject to periodic verification can be calibrated directly on the measurement object based on the concept of online calibration, which consists in connecting an additional GPS signal to the MEMS sensors to obtain the absolute value of time imposed on the measurement results of quantities, and using a special microcontroller “Smart-Up-Unit”, which can contain one or more MEMS sensors and has the ability to connect to external timers to provide real-time pre-processing of measured data.

The sensor calibrated in this way can be connected to web services that simplify integration into Industry 4.0 and the Internet of Things. Thus, using mathematical methods, all mounted MEMS sensors can be calibrated simultaneously. This procedure is called one-touch calibration.

Manufacturing of the future in accordance with the concept of Industry 4.0 is largely based on networked sensor technology and intelligent assessment methods. Therefore, metrology concepts, procedures and standards in Industry 4.0 are necessary to build an appropriate metrology infrastructure. The entire lifecycle of data must be considered, from the measuring instruments to the decisions made based on that data.

Traceable calibration of measurement equipment is the basis for every accurate measurement, so measurement results are reliable, comparable and repeatable. The development of basic metrology research in recent decades has generally focused on improved accuracy, new measured variables, and new measurement principles. However, with greater integration of digital technologies into instrumentation, the rapidly growing use of sensor networks, and the trend toward embedded preprocessing in so-called “intelligent sensors,” entirely new development approaches are required. For example, low-cost MEMS sensors are available in extremely large quantities and make traditional calibration approaches uneconomical. Digital outputs no longer allow separation of sensor and calibration preprocessing. Embedded systems add significant complexity to preprocessing methods. Thus, the next decade will open up new areas of research and development for metrology support in Industry 4.0.

A sensor network is not only a spatially distributed measuring system, but in general a network of measuring and information systems that can contain many heterogeneous sensor elements. In this case, the consideration of measurement uncertainty, as a rule, does not correspond to the principles of metrology [13-15], but is followed by such strategies as reliable control or assessment, as, for example,

in [16-19]. Integrating such developments with GUM principles and its methodology requires fundamental research into application-oriented applications of the GUM guidelines [20 - 22], but this requires flexible software solutions. This means a paradigm shift for most metrological scientific settings. A key challenge in this combination of machine learning techniques, smart sensors and other technology elements is maintaining trust in the data, algorithms and processes. We are talking about data quality, which directly depends on the availability of the concept of measurement uncertainty to support the metrological infrastructure [13, 14]. To capture the entire information flow, such an infrastructure must, inter alia, include traceability of smart sensor calibration taking into account time-dependent effects, metrology processing of complex sensor networks, and uncertainty assessment for data aggregation and decision-making methods.

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